

Supporting Information

Electrochemical CO reduction in zero-gap electrolyzers necessitates careful water management.

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SI Note 1: Methods and Materials

Electrolyser configurations chosen for the purposes of this study, are schematically depicted in Figure S 1 and technical details of the different configurations are mentioned below –

- a) Catholyte GDE: The working electrode area was set to 0.5 cm^2 by rubber gaskets. The counter electrode was a 1.5 cm^2 iridium coated gas diffusion layer (GDL). Humidified CO_2 was purged from behind the catalyst through a serpentine flow pattern at a constant flow rate of 30 ml/min . The electrolyte in both chambers was recirculated using a peristaltic pump set at flow rates of 21 ml/min . Both electrolytes were separated and fed through reservoirs of 25 ml volume. The current collectors for both the working and counter electrodes were made of gold coated stainless steel.

Figure S 1 Schematic illustration of the three different cell configurations - a) Catholyte GDE, b) Zerogap GDE

- b) Zerogap GDE: The zerogap GDE cell configuration (eChemicles Zrt., CO_2 electrolyzer test cell) was based on the designs reported in the publications of Endrődi et al¹⁻³. The Cu coated gas diffusion layer (working area - 8 cm^2) was placed on top of a stainless steel cathodic current collector and was held in place by a $200\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ -thick PTFE spacer which resulted in a GDL compression of $\sim 20\%$ in relation to its original thickness. The

anode compartment consisted of Ir coated Ti frits with the Ir coated side facing the Cu coated cathode. The two compartments were separated and were in mechanical contact with an anion-exchange membrane. Humidified CO₂ was fed to the system at a constant flow rate of 60 ml/min using a Bronkhorst El-Flow prestige mass flow controller. Feed gas humidification was achieved by flowing the gas through 15 ml mili-Q water in a gastight 100ml DURAN bottle. The anode side consisted of an electrolyte solution recirculating through the porous Ti frits. The electrolyte was recirculated using a peristaltic pump at a constant flow rate of 21 ml/min.

The protocols for electrode preparation, electrochemical testing, product analysis, and spectroscopic data analysis are given in our previous publication.^{4,5}

SI Note 2: Electrochemical test setup

Figure S 2 Schematic of the electrochemical test station showing the different components used for a zero-gap experiments.

SI Note 3: Additional electrocatalysis data

Figure S 3 Faradaic efficiency and measured current data for COR experiments using Cu-GDEs with 9% Nafion

Figure S 4 Faradaic efficiency and measured current data for COR experiments using Cu-GDEs with 13% Nafion

Figure S 5 Faradaic efficiency and measured current data for COR experiments using Cu-GDEs with 26% Nafion

Figure S 6 Selectivity trends plotted as a function of the contact angle for CO-fed zero-gap electrolyzers

Figure S 7 Nafion concentration dependent selectivity trends for CO₂-fed zero-gap electrolyzers

Figure S 8 Faradaic efficiency and measured current data for CO₂R experiments using Cu-GDEs with 26% Nafion

Figure S 9 Faradaic efficiency and measured current data for CO₂R experiments using Cu-GDEs without Nafion

Figure S 10 Faradaic efficiency and measured current data for CO₂R experiments using Cu-GDEs without Nafion

SI Note 4: XPS Analysis

Figure S 11 Cu LMM Auger spectra for as prepared samples with different Nafion w/w%.

References

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2. Endrődi, B. *et al.* Operando cathode activation with alkali metal cations for high current density operation of water-fed zero-gap carbon dioxide electrolyzers. *Nat. Energy* **6**, 439–448 (2021).
3. Endrődi, B. *et al.* Multilayer Electrolyzer Stack Converts Carbon Dioxide to Gas Products at High Pressure with High Efficiency. *ACS Energy Lett.* **4**, 1770–1777 (2019).
4. El-Nagar, G. A., Haun, F., Gupta, S., Stojkovicj, S. & Mayer, M. T. Unintended cation crossover influences CO₂ reduction selectivity in Cu-based zero-gap electrolyzers. *Nat. Commun.* **14**, 2062 (2023).
5. Stojkovicj, S. *et al.* Electrocatalyst Derived from Waste Cu–Sn Bronze for CO₂ Conversion into CO. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **13**, 38161–38169 (2021).